

Supplemental Figure 1

Supplemental Table 3 Rate of integrity and risk of bias

PMID	Author	Year	Strategy	In.Vitro.Cytotoxicity.Method	Medium	Serum	Cytokine	Stimulant	Culture.time	Transduction.time	Transduction.efficiency	Gene.structure.or.sequence	ET	Antibody.concentration	Control	Errorbar	Abnormal.value	Random	Mice.age.sex.weight	Endpoint
15287953	Rischer M	2004	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	no	no	NA	NA	NA
23295945	Deniger DC	2013	CAR	Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes
27598655	Du SH	2016	CAR	DELFLA® EuTDA Cytotoxicity Reagents kit	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes
28818060	Harrer DC	2017	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
28341563	Fisher J	2017	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
29310916	Capsomidis A	2018	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
29402645	Xiao L	2018	CAR	DELFLA® EuTDA Cytotoxicity Reagents kit	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
31824502	Polito VA	2019	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
31506382	Fisher J	2019	CAR	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
32714329	Rozenbaum M	2020	CAR	apoptosis by Annexin V- Cy5 reagent	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	no
32671190	Fleischer LC	2020	CAR	VPD450	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	NA	no	unclear	unclear	NA	NA	NA
32462079	Ang WX	2020	CAR	DELFLA® EuTDA Cytotoxicity Reagents kit	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	yes
33520361	Zhai X	2021	CAR	CFSE/7-AAD	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes
34916256	Makkouk A	2021	CAR	RFlucexpressing tumor target	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
35136603	Nishimoto KP	2022	CAR	RFluc-expressing 18-h luciferase cytotoxicity assay, and IncuCyte® Immune Cell Killing Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	yes
35711450	Ferry GM	2022	CAR	IFNγ and CD107a; chromium (51Cr)-release assay for 0n-transduced;	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	NA	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA	NA
35295709	Ye X	2022	CAR	CCK-8	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
36162920	Sánchez Martínez D	2022	CAR	eFluor 670/7-AAD	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	yes
35496793	Parente-Pereira AC	2022	CAR	ffLuc+ BxPC3 tumor	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes
35709135	Zhang X	2022	CAR	DELFLA® EuTDA Cytotoxicity Reagents kit	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	yes
37078788	Huang SW	2023	CAR	DiOC18 stained target	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes
37387794	Becker SA	2023	CAR	Violet Proliferation Dye 450 /7-AAD/ Annexin V	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	yes
37446055	Wang Y	2023	CAR	X-Celligence RTCA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no
37134157	Frieling JS	2023	CAR	X-Celligence RTCA	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
37938576	Lee D	2023	CAR	FG-labeled tumor cells	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	yes

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37770968	Wang Y	2023	CAR	assessed by measuring the diameter changes of PTCs	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
16540688	van der Veken LT	2006	TCR-T	Target cells were labeled with 100 µCi Na51 2 CrO4	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
19242528	Hiasa A	2009	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	unclear	unclear	NA	NA	NA
21566093	Marcu-Malina V	2011	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	no	no
21909128	Zhao H	2012	TCR-T	MTT assay	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
23018643	Gründer C	2012	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	no
26121617	Shimizu K	2015	TCR-T	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
25991821	Straetemans T	2015	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	no
27463149	He K	2016	TCR-T	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
28259946	Tao C	2017	TCR-T	calcein AM (CAM) release assay	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
29122757	Legut M	2018	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
30552102	Benveniste PM	2018	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	unclear	unclear	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	no	no	NA	NA	NA
29899740	Straetemans T	2018	TCR-T	IFNγ ELISPOT	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA	NA
30479831	Xu Y	2018	TCR-T	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
30871629	Johanna I	2019	TCR-T	IFNγ ELISPOT	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	NA	yes	unclear	no
32019779	Janssen A	2020	TCR-T	IFNγ ELISPOT	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	unclear	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA	NA
31585951	Kierkels	2019	TCR-T	IFNγ	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	NA	yes	yes	NA	no	no	yes
32022317	Johanna I	2020	TCR-T	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	unclear	yes
32780528	Ichiki Y	2020	TCR-T	51-Chromium release assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	no	yes	no	no	no
34575700	Strijker JGM	2021	TCR-T	Live-Cell Imaging System Incucyte from Sartorius	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
34759930	Johanna I	2021	TCR-T	IFNγ ELISPOT	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	NA	yes	unclear	yes
35776199	He P	2023	TCR-T	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	no	no	yes	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
37349298	Chen Z	2023	TCR-T	Fixable viability dye and Annexin V	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
36681817	Li C	2023	TCR-T	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	no
18782650	Wang Z	2008	antibody	MTT assay	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	unclear	no
23920126	Zheng J	2013	antibody	LDH activity using the CytoTox 96 0n-Radioactive Cytotoxicity Assay Kit	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
24448235	Oberg HH	2014	antibody	51-Chromium release assay	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
25979810	Oberg HH	2015	antibody	Real Time Cell Analyzer (RTCA) single-plate system	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
27825135	Schiller CB	2016	antibody	X-Celligence RTCA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA

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28708284	Peipp M	2017	antibody	51-Chromium release assay	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
29296532	de Bruin RCG	2017	antibody	CFSE/7-AAD	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	no
29725336	Oberg HH	2018	antibody	51-Chromium release assay	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
32588076	Guo Q	2020	antibody	CFSE/PI	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
31833593	Oberg HH	2020	antibody	X-Celligence RTCA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	unclear	yes	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
33177109	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	mCherry or CFSE/MitoTracker Orange and To-pro-3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
33526858	Ganesan R	2021	antibody	CFSE/7-AAD	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	unclear	no
33451981	de Weerd I	2021	antibody	CFSE or Cell Trace Violet/7-AAD or Mitotracker Orange and To-pro-3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
34815357	van Diest E	2021	antibody	Luciferase based cytotoxicity	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
34040604	Yang R	2021	antibody	CFSE/PI	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	no
36096643	Lai AY	2022	antibody	Apoptracker Green	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
36868236	Lameris R	2023	antibody	PBSE/annexin-V/7-AAD	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	unclear	yes
36685546	van Diest E	2023	antibody	Luciferase based cytotoxicity	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA
23326319	Lamb LS Jr	2013	gene modification	Targets were labeled with the membrane dye PKH26	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	no	no	NA	NA	NA
32368439	Wang Y	2018	vaccine	CCK-8	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	NA	NA	NA	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	NA	NA	NA
30594069	Li L	2019	extracellular vesicles (gdTDEs)	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	no	no
34702850	Lamb LS	2021	gene modification	CFSE/7-AAD	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	NA	no	no	no	no	no	yes
37835538	Li HK	2023	antibody-cell conjugation	CellTiter-Glo® luminescent cell viability assay	yes	yes	yes	yes	unclear	NA	NA	yes	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	no	unclear	no
37857598	Wang Y	2023	gene modification	LDH Release Assay	yes	yes	no	unclear	unclear	yes	yes	no	yes	NA	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	no